

PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF A MACHINE-LEARNING BASED CHARACTERIZATION OF ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAM PATTERNS IN SLEEP-RELATED PATHOLOGIES

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Abstract— Electroencephalography (EEG) patterns typically change in association with different types of sleep-related pathologies, with respect to normal patterns observed in control groups. Several of these changes have been well described in the scientific literature, based mainly on frequency-domain analyses for each pathology. However, the case-by-case nature of these studies, together with the inherent complexity of EEG signals, represents a challenge in obtaining complete characterizations for other pathologies, and many studies thus focus on combining features from different types of signals. In this paper, we present a machine-learning approach for detecting EEG-only changes in different pathologies. We apply different classifiers to frequency-domain EEG features and compare these features over control and experimental groups. Our study cases initially focus on nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy (NFLE), narcolepsy, bruxism, insomnia, rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder, obstructive sleep-disordered breathing, and periodic limb movement disorder. However, in this preliminary study, we provide results regarding NFLE, for which we provide the initial tests. Our results suggest that the use of random forests (RFs) and support vector machines (SVMs) can potentially distinguish the control and experimental groups based solely on EEG features, although the accuracies are still limited. The use of convolutional neural networks, on the other hand, did not provide improved detection, possibly due to the limited number of training cases. In the next stages of the research, we will focus on applying feature selection methods, to try and improve the detection performance when using RFs and SVMs, for NFLE and for the other described pathologies.

Keywords — *Electroencephalography, nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy, narcolepsy, bruxism, machine learning.*

I. Introduction

Sleep constitutes the normal suspension of consciousness in terms of behavior, and by the presence of specific brain waves, regarding electrophysiology [1, 2]. Sleep occurs in all mammals and probably in all vertebrates [2, 3].

Due to the importance of sleep, studies have been carried out to better understand it [1]. Studies associated with sleep occur at different scales, background contexts, and perspectives, such as in the neurobiology of sleep from a genetic point of view [4, 6], cellular aspects [4, 7, 8] and cognitive aspects [4, 5, 8].

Evidence points to the quality of sleep as being as important for health as an adequate diet or the practice of physical activities [3, 9, 10]. Sleep deprivation can thus alter levels of alertness, perception, learning, and memory [2, 11, 12]. Furthermore, it can lead to false memory formation [13] and to metabolic, cardiovascular, and immunological disfunction [6].

In this context, it is vital to understand the physiology associated with sleep. This includes recognizing normal and altered patterns observed at different sleep stages and during sleep deprivation. Such understanding is essential to diagnose pathologies at early stages, allowing for effective treatments.

Therefore, many sleep studies focus on evaluating several types of bioelectrical and biomechanical signals that are known to change depending on the sleep stage and/or sleep quality, such as in analysis of polysomnography records [14, 15, 16]. This approach has led to important findings regarding physiological changes associated to sleep levels and sleep pathologies. Recent proposed methods include machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms applied to classifying such signals [17, 18, 19, 20].

However, many studies we found in the current scientific literature focus on evaluating combinations of many signals, on a case-by-case basis according to the considered pathology or to the type of sleep analysis. These studies use but are not limited to electroencephalography (EEG) signals [17, 18, 19, 20]. The case-by-case nature of these studies, together with the inherent complexity of EEG signals, represents a challenge in determining up to which point EEG signals alone can be used to obtain complete characterizations for other pathologies, and in determining such characterizations.

Given this research gap, the present work proposes a

comparison between sleeping EEG signals amongst a control group and groups affected by different pathologies (one in each experimental group). It considers the problem of sleep diagnoses using features extracted from EEG signals only, in different frequency bands, using feature extraction and classical classifiers.

We initially analyze different bands with different models, hyperparameters of the models in question, and different EEG channels. We evaluate whether a region or number of regions may be more or less important to this task, considering the distribution of data from the used datasets. Initially, we use binary classifiers in the identification of nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy (NFLE), which is the class with the highest number of individuals within the available polysomnography records. Also, the relevance of studying NFLE is associated to its complex diagnosis [21] as well as its severe health impacts. In fact, NFLE can be a very debilitating disease, as it can lead to deficits in memory and other intellectual abilities, as well as deficits in visuo-spatial performance and negative impacts in social interactions [21]. Nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy is also called sleep-related hypermotor epilepsy (SHE) in some recent studies [21].

In our future studies, we will extend our methods for characterizing narcolepsy, bruxism, insomnia, rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder (RBD), obstructive sleep-disordered breathing (SDB), and periodic limb movement disorder (PLM). These conditions vary in terms of diagnostic aspects and health impacts [22].

II. Materials and Methods

A. Description of the DataSet

In order to implement the proposed feature extraction procedures, and evaluate the classification strategies over these features, we used control and experimental signals from a dataset of polysomnography records. This set is the so-called Cyclic Alternating Pattern (CAP) database [23], and it is publicly available as a PhysioNet [24] repository.

For each subject, the CAP database contains individual electroencephalography (EEG), electromyography (EMG), and electrocardiography (EKG) signals. It has data from 16 subjects who do not present any diagnostic of neurological pathologies and are not considered under the effects of medicine which could potentially influence the central nervous system. The other 92 subjects in the dataset are divided in the following groups: 40 subjects diagnosed with NFLE; 22 subjects affected by RBD; 10 subjects affected by PLM; 9 subjects affected insomnia; 5 subjects with narcolepsy; 4 subjects with SDB; and 2 subjects with bruxism. Also, the dataset includes female (42) and male (65) subjects, aged between 14 and 80 years – the mean age is 45 years; 40 for our target (NFLE) and 54 years for the others.

B. Pre-Processing and Feature Extraction

All data was locally saved, and the EEG files were converted to the parquet format using the Pandas multi-electrode analysis (MNE) library, in Python. The available EEG information is in the time domain and corresponds to different durations, depending on the subject.

In our proposed method, we apply the 1024-point discrete Fourier transform (DFT) to each signal, in order to extract spectral information represented as the energy over 60 consecutive frequency bands, without intersection. This procedure also allows the data for each participant to have the same dimension: 60 attributes, each one representing the energy computed over a specific frequency band. The comparatively high number of chosen bands was based on experimental tests, which suggested a better performance in the subsequent classification tests, for the available signals. Also, the sampling frequency at which the available EEG signals were acquired ($f_s=512\text{ Hz}$), which is considered sufficient and even high for EEG signals, lead to a high spectral resolution, so information can be properly evaluated at those bands. We also recall that most of the signal information is concentrated on the lower bands, for EEG signals.

The results are saved in the comma-separated value (CSV) format. Each of the CSV files corresponds to an electrode. In these files, each line is the distribution of power to a subject, whereas each column corresponds to a specific frequency band. The electrodes follow the “10-20” EEG assembly pattern, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Representation of the international standard 10-20 for mounting EEG electrodes in humans. Parts A and B of the figure show different perspectives of the same assembly; the part C shows an extended version of the 10-20 model. Each circle represents an electrode with its respective denomination in the center of each circle. Figure adapted from [22].

In the proposed system, we selected only four derivations taken from the distribution in Figure 1: C4-A1, C4-P3, F4-C4 and P4-O2. This selection was performed in order to maximize the number of universally available derivations in the dataset. In fact, recordings of these particular derivations were present for 97 of the 108 subjects, whereas any combination of a larger number of derivations was present only in fewer subjects. Subsets of these four derivations were also considered, to verify whether a lower number of derivations was sufficient for any of the proposed classification tasks, in a considered model.

C. Classifier Implementation

Based on the extracted features, we implemented classifiers based on support vector machines (SVMs), and Random Forests (Rfs). We also used convolutional neural networks (CNNs), but in this case the classifiers were applied directly to the input EEG signals, as opposed to previously

extracted spectral features.

In all cases, the available data was first divided into training and test sets. The corresponding classifier was trained using only on the training set, whereas the test set was used for the performance evaluation based on objective metrics. This general training/testing procedure was repeated for a total of $k=20$ times, where at each time we used a different test set, without intersection between the test sets, according to the k -fold cross-validation approach [25].

The aim of our experiments is to compare different classifiers and different models under the proposed preprocessing scenarios. To do that, we used the following combinations of hyperparameters. For the SVMs, we used four different kernels: the kernel corresponding to linear transformations of the features, the kernel corresponding to a polynomial (poly) transformation of the features, the Gaussian radial basis function (RBF), and the sigmoid function. For the RFs, we used the maximum depths of 1, 2, 5, 10, 15, and 25. For the CNNs we used 8 different models with different combinations of activation functions (the rectified linear unit, or RELU, the softmax, and the hiperbolic tangent functions), with and without dropout layers. Each CNN model includes convolutional and maxpooling layers as well. These CNN configurations allow the classifier to learn the relevant data characteristics, without the explicit feature extraction carried out in the case of the SVM and RF models.

The use of these different types of models is described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of approaches, algorithms, and architectures used in the experiments. There are two main comparison domains, first using a preliminary explicit spectral analysis for feature extraction and then with the feature extraction performed directly by the classifier itself. In the first case, there is a comparison of electrodes, in addition to the comparison between using SVM and RF (each with several experiments comparing some hyperparameters). In the second case, we have experiments with CNN hyperparameters comparison.

The experiment consists of three steps, in order to attain the comparisons of the classifiers. Figure 3 summarizes these steps. The first one corresponds to the evaluation of performance metrics of the SVM and RF models, with the different proposed parameters and using an arbitrary set of derivations (amongst the four originally selected electrodes). In this step, we consider the kernel variation for the SVMs and the depth variation for the RFs. Based on the results, we chose the parameters that lead to greater accuracies. In the second step, we compared other derivations to verify whether any of them corresponds to more relevant regions in the study. In the last step, we considered the convolutional neural networks with the different proposed architectures.

Figure 4: Steps of the proposed experiments. Initially, an electrode is chosen arbitrarily for the evaluation of the algorithms and some approaches are compared using SVMs and RFs. Then, the algorithm with the best result is used in the comparison between different electrodes. The electrode with the best result is used in the last step for evaluating the architectures.

III. Results

The obtained results were analyzed with a focus on evaluating the models' performance in the task of classifying sleep-related pathologies.

In this preliminary study, there was no signal windowing or resampling strategies. Thus, considering the low number of participants, we used a small number of samples (one per participant). Therefore, in order to increase the power of generalization of the model, and to minimize the bias of the data in the training from this unbalanced base, a binary classifier was implemented (thus reducing the the number of classes). We choose to classify whether the sample belongs to the class "nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy" (class with the highest number of available samples).

According to the proposed methodology, the first step compares SVM and RF models. Next, different electrodes are compared. Finally, convolutional neural networks were compared regarding the best precedent result.

A. Step 1: using electrode “F4-C4”, compare the best parameters for SVM and for RF

First, we compared the accuracy of models using SVM and RF with different parameters. These are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Based on these results, the parameters were chosen, according to the highest observed accuracies.

Table 1. Comparison of accuracy of models using SVM, with the derivation “F4-C4”, and for the different tested kernel.

Exp.	Elect.	Classif.	Par.	Acc.	SD
1	F4-C4	SVM	Linear	0.61	0.02
2	F4-C4	SVM	Poly	0.59	0.03
3	F4-C4	SVM	RBF	0.61	0.02
4	F4-C4	SVM	Sigmoid	0.61	0.02

Table 2. Comparison of accuracy of models using RF, with the derivation “F4-C4” and varying the depth of the trees

Exp.	Elect.	Classif.	Par.	M. Acc.	SD
1	F4-C4	RF	1	0.61	0.02
2	F4-C4	RF	5	0.57	0.06
3	F4-C4	RF	10	0.57	0.07
4	F4-C4	RF	15	0.57	0.07

Regarding the SVM models, we obtained comparable results for the tested kernels here designed by the terms *linear*, *poly* and *sigmoid*, which represent, respectively, the kernels corresponding to linear transformations of the features, to polynomial transformations of the features, and to the sigmoid function. Among these kernels, the *poly* option was chosen. Note the *linear* option is computationally less expensive, but in other tasks in the literature it has a lower probability of generating properly separation hypersurfaces, depending on the classification problem. In other cases, it can lead to underfitting. On the other hand, using the *poly* option instead of the *sigmoid* one was, for now, an arbitrary choice, though we will perform further tests in the next experimentations.

By comparing the results for the models using RFs, we observed that the classifier with depth 1 had better accuracy. This indicates that the choice of depth of the trees in the RF can be a decisive factor in the performance of this classifier.

B. Step 2: electrode comparison

Based on these results for SVM and RF models, we made a new comparison using different electrodes in new classifiers using the chosen parameters in step 1. The accuracy results did not change with electrode changes.

Overall, this result indicates that: (i) the parameters chosen in the first step can be robust enough to handle the characteristics of the data; (ii) the choice of these electrodes may not be critical for the classification task – the signals’ features of interest can potentially be homogeneously distributed over the scalp.

In this sense, it is worth mentioning that, although the temporal resolution of the EEG is good when compared, for example, to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), its spatial resolution is much lower.

This aspect may be related to the independence of the electrode in the results, for the features we used.

In addition, it is possible that there is variation in the

results between other electrodes in areas other than those studied, as only four were considered.

C. Step 3: Comparisons with CNN

Finally, we implemented different convolutional neural networks, with different numbers of layers. The layers include one-dimensional domain convolutional layers, followed by different types of activation functions (rectified linear unit, softmax, and hyperbolic tangent). Also, we tested models with and without 0.5-rate dropouts. Table 3 summarizes the tested architectures.

Table 3. Architectures and hyperparameters used in the tested convolutional neural network models.

Model	Conv. Layers	Activ. Funct.	Drop.	Pool.	Dense Layers
1	2	ReLU	0.5	Max Pooling	2
2	1	Softmax	-	-	1
3	1	Tanh	-	-	1
4	1	Tanh	-	-	2
5	1	Tanh	-	-	2
6	3	Tanh, Sigmoid	0.5	Max Pooling	2
7	1	Tanh	-	-	1
8	1	Tanh	-	-	1

All CNN models were unable to properly classify the input signals, as these models showed a bias towards one of the possible classes.

A possible reason for this result is the comparatively low number of training examples in the dataset, for the case of models that do not rely on previously extracted features and therefore must learn to extract the relevant information. This paradigm typically requires more training examples, compared to models that use previous feature engineering, as in the case of the SVMs and RFs we used. Another possible reason is the choice of architecture: layers, number of filters, activation functions, and dropout rates. Therefore, we will perform further analyzes regarding both the CNN architectures and the training and test sets.

Class imbalance is another reason that may have contributed to this problem. As there is imbalance, the model can become biased to the majority class and have difficulty recognizing patterns of cases from the minority class.

IV. Further Discussion of the Detection Results

Our preliminary results align with the complex nature of EEG signals, and the challenges that come with detecting subtle changes that may signify specific sleep-related pathologies. Detecting such changes using previously extracted spectral features, as opposed to training a CNN to classify the EEG signals in raw format, seemed for feasible, at least for the comparable low number of available training signals.

The use of machine learning classifiers, especially SVMs and RFs, has shown promise in discerning differences between control and experimental groups, based on the proposed spectral EEG features. This underscores the

potential of machine learning models in automating the detection and classification of sleep disorders, which traditionally rely on expert analysis. One significant implication of this study, which may be particularly promising for future investigations, is the observed robustness in the chosen parameters across different electrodes. This suggests that EEG features relevant for distinguishing NFLE might be uniformly represented across various scalp regions, thus providing flexibility in electrode choice and paving the way for more scalable diagnostic tools.

Moreover, the preliminary results indicate that the number and location of the electrodes might not be critical factors in this classification task, given the homogeneity of the data across the scalp. This could be especially important in settings where resources or technical equipment might be limited. Nevertheless, a more extensive analysis is still needed, incorporating more electrodes from various regions, to affirm this notion further. The performance of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) highlighted a well-known challenge in machine learning: the necessity of vast datasets for training this type of model. CNNs, which have seen great success in other studies, appear to underperform in this specific EEG classification task, due to the limited dataset, highlighting the importance of the size and quality of the training data when selecting a machine-learning model.

We also emphasize that the comparatively high performance of SVMs and RFs over CNNs in this study offers valuable insights into feature extraction. The SVMs and RFs used frequency-domain features (spectral energy distributions), which are commonly associated to sleep patterns. On the other hand, CNNs, which automatically extract features, might need more extensive datasets to discern and learn the relevant information from raw EEG signals. This balance between manual feature engineering and automated feature learning is a topic for our next experiments.

V. Conclusion

This study offers an initial assessment of machine learning-based characterization of EEG patterns in diagnosing sleep-related pathologies, particularly nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy. Our preliminary results highlight the potential of support vector machines and random forests in effectively distinguishing EEG features, while the proposed convolutional neural networks require further optimization, particularly given the constraints of the available dataset size. The study's findings underscore the importance of leveraging domain knowledge in feature engineering, and the observed robustness across different electrodes hints at a more flexible and scalable diagnostic approach in the future. As research progresses, refining these techniques could improve the diagnosis of sleep disorders, thereby improving patient care and outcomes.

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